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Management development: The total process embracing informal and formal processes

Abstract

This paper provides a conceptual understanding of management development (MD). The paper emphasises the need to utilise both formal and informal processes in MD. As much of the managerial learning by experience is unplanned and unstructured, informal managerial learning is a by-product of a variety of managerial tasks, the dynamic nature of managerial priorities, changes in the working environment, and changes in colleagues and bosses, which all provide new opportunities and stimuli. So, excluding them takes the MD away from reality and eliminates from conscious consideration several potential opportunities for learning. On the other hand, simple reliance on opportunities to learn from experience was not claimed to be the best answer to MD. Managers recognise gaps in their experience, and they could visualise the extent to which the opportunities could have been better recognised or the processes could have been better managed by their bosses. On the other hand, there is a growing use of formal development processes to help managers learn. Therefore, the paper describes MD that embraces the total process, including both formal and informal processes, and finally addresses the trends in and challenges to MD.

Keywords: Formal processes, Informal processes, Management development

Introduction

The environmental factors have been changing theorists' and practitioners' views on competitiveness. In today's business environment, high-quality human resources are valuable, rare, difficult to imitate, and not subject to substitution. If managed effectively, human resources are the most expensive and valuable asset of an organization. Hence, the development of this asset is crucial to the success of any organization. In this respect, HRD focuses on learning experiences provided by organizations to achieve its goals by viewing people as assets rather than costs, by being proactive rather than reactive, and by balancing employee interests and organizational concerns (Bender et al., 1996). In the international context, too, learning, knowledge acquisition, and adaptation are important rationales for the creation of international businesses that contribute significantly to international business performance. Hence, HRD efforts continue to be an essential element for organizations striving for excellence.

Being a component of HRD, management development (MD) has become accepted by researchers and writers as an important means of developing managers to make the best use of resources. Researchers emphasise the importance of MD for economic growth and success, for the organization, and for the individual. It is said that a country can have endless resources of all sorts, but unless it has better management, the lower the output and its quality will be. Thus, management capability is a critical factor in any economic system (Schaafsma, 1996). Further, effective management is vital for organizational success. Companies do not receive immediate returns on the time managers spend on MD, yet the growth of the companies demands upgrading of managerial skills (Lawler et al., 1995). On the other hand, the provision of MD can increase the level of commitment of managers to the organization and increase their perceptions that the organization is a good place to work (Akuratiyagamage and Opatha, 2003; Schuler, 1987). Therefore, MD undertaken by organizations indicates commitment to managers, while the recipients are more likely to feel valued as an individual who is always searching and trying to develop his/her capabilities.

In developing managers, organizations can use two processes, namely informal and formal development processes. Informal MD processes are by-products of organizational activities, such as task accomplishment or interpersonal interaction, and managers may not set out intentionally and explicitly to learn something through pre-planned means (Marsick and Watkins, 1997; Mumford, 1997). Formal MD processes, on the other hand, include institutionally sponsored, planned, and deliberate processes. Thus, formal processes are often monitored and controlled by people and forces other than the individual manager involved (Akuratiyagamage, 2003; Marsick and Watkins, 1997; Mumford, 1997).

Informal MD processes

It has often been said that managers learn to manage by managing through experience. Experience is the process of engaging in an act or situation, and experience is considered by some management writers and practitioners to be indeed the best teacher (Doyle and Young, 2000). Learning is most likely to result from experience, which is relevant and significant to the individual (Doyle and Young, 2000). Thus, informal development usually occurs during the course of managers' everyday work. For instance, managers learn while carrying out responsibilities of the job, projects, presentations, committee meetings, and business visits; managers learn every time they are confronted with an unusual problem, an unfamiliar task, or

a move to a different job (Mumford, 1997; Armstrong, 1999). Further, early job challenges, early broad responsibilities, and early leadership opportunities can also have developmental significance. Thus, these informal development incidents are by-products of some other activities, such as task accomplishment, interpersonal interaction, sensing the organizational culture, trial-and-error experimentation, or even from the interactions they have with their superiors, peers, subordinates, and customers. The most significant feature of informal development incidents is that, though informal development opportunities almost always take place naturally, managers are not always conscious that they are in developmental experiences at all. Therefore, most of the informal incidences occur due to organizational decisions that are made wholly or largely in order to meet organizational objectives and may have nothing to do with the development of the individual. Because of this, these situations are essentially ad hoc, informal, and accidental; not actually designed for developmental purposes. Therefore, informal development incidents are the tip of an iceberg, in two senses. First, they are a tiny proportion of the full range of incidents from managerial work that provide learning experiences. Second, they are the tip of an iceberg for any particular individual. Therefore, though informal, accidental experiences are widely present and often provide the deepest and richest learning, they are often badly identified and, in consequence, insufficiently used. However, there are four different approaches to learn from informal development incidences (Mumford, 1997), namely, managers learn unconsciously from experience, where learning occurs through some natural process of osmosis; learning emerges by reflecting on difficulties, mishaps and frustrations, which often provide the spur for the incidental learner; learning occurs more consciously by thinking about what has happened and reaching conclusions; learning occurs by seeing future events not merely as management requirements, but as events from which it is possible to learn.

However, because there are no specified developmental goals as such accompanied by informal development incidents, managers generally learn if they analyse what they did and determine how and why those contributed to success or failure. This retrospective or reflective learning will only be effective if managers can apply those successfully in the future (Armstrong, 1999). Therefore, the effective use of learning opportunities depends on the conscious attempt to improve the design of the opportunities on the one hand, and the understanding of the learner about learning processes on the other (Mumford, 1997). Hence, if managers know the advantages of retrospective learning and the possibilities of linking them to prospective learning, unintentional learning can be a basis for further intentional learning. On the other

hand, meeting organizational challenges leaves little choice but to absorb, unconsciously and by some process of osmosis, lessons from their experience and develop new abilities. In this respect, development comes from inside, from individuals who desire to succeed. Therefore, development is not something that could be done to or for someone. Development is something people do for themselves. But, as mentioned earlier, managers differ in their preferred approach to learning. Some managers may enjoy learning from experience, whereas others may not. Therefore, informal learning has to be deliberately encouraged by an organization (Woodall, 2000). Organizations can provide kinds of challenges that will provide managers with opportunities to develop new skills/abilities. The developmental potential of work experience is driven by the challenges it presents. While exposure can be useful, even enriching, what matters is what one is doing while being exposed. If organizations wish to encourage informal learning, then individuals need support in maintaining openness towards new experiences and perspectives, support in disciplined reflection, and support in translating the learning into practice. The key tools to facilitate informal learning are planning for learning, creating mechanisms for learning, and developing an environment conducive to learning.

In this context, managers and their bosses have to identify prospective learning opportunities and should subsequently review the extent to which individual managers have taken advantage of them (Mumford, 1997). Such identification is always looking back retrospectively to learn from past experience. Every time what needs to be learnt should be linked to work situations. This empowers the learner to begin learning by thinking about what they want to master, improve, or change (Megginson et al., 1999). Managers can find learning experiences not only by thinking and reviewing normal managerial activities but also by reviewing various kinds of (mainly written) material (Mumford, 1997). Some of such written materials are job description; activity list or daily/weekly reminder of things to do; work diary that may simply indicate some of the most important events on daily basis; a learning log, where a manager deliberately keeps a review of learning experiences and opportunities; discussions with colleagues, where one or more colleagues identify similar activities and experience which may provide learning; individual discussions with boss, where some specific activity is related to a learning opportunity. Therefore, individuals have to make an effort in the identification of learning incidents. In the planning process, personal development plans that are developed in concert between managers, their superiors, and often external learning facilitators, play a vital part. However, an informal learning experience is not educational unless it is purposive. The objective or purpose guides the process of learning. When the purpose is clear, managers can

observe surrounding conditions better; they can learn from the knowledge of what has happened in similar situations in the past. Further, the purpose guides to learn from the knowledge that is obtained by recollection, and from information, advice, and warnings of those who have a wider experience. In identifying purpose, it is much more likely to involve other people, probably the manager and the boss in most situations, or perhaps the manager and one or more colleagues. It is partly through this process of openness, sharing, and partnership that some of the weaknesses of learning from experience can be reduced. In addition, on one hand, one of the features of managerial experience as a learning process is that managers have to plan/pre-decide informal learning without separating learning from experience, where learning is tied to real-life problems and experience. Though learning takes place “just in time” while struggling with a challenge, this cannot happen without time to learn, feedback, and other forms of assistance (Marsick and Watkins, 1997). On the other hand, managers may have no choice in the managerial experience. They have to learn from them. Failure to learn from experience might not be the result of deliberate and conscious avoidance but simply failure to recognise the opportunity or ignorance about how to learn from it most effectively (Mumford, 1997). In this context, a manager’s insight alone is insufficient; they need organizational support, which encourages individuals to grow, accepts individuals who have changed, and promotes the retention of new behaviours. Therefore, facilitation is vital at this point of the process. The contemporary view of HRD stresses that what an individual manager has learnt has to flow freely within the organization (Marsick and Watkins, 1997). In this regard, what is most important is that such individual learning has to flow from the individuals, and those have to be captured and used by other members of the organization. Hence, developing an environment conducive to learning is vital. Learning has to be pursued consciously and deliberately for profit (Kolb, 1996). Managers and organizations should budget time specifically to learn from their experience. For example, when important meetings are held or important decisions are made, time should be set aside to critique and learn from these events (Kolb, 1996). Further, managers have to have the freedom to influence outcomes by taking risks and doing things differently (Megginson and Whitaker, 1999). Furthermore, though informal learning occurs naturally, managers have to analyse their interpretations; otherwise, their false assumptions can lead them to inaccurate conclusions. Hence, reflection is the primary tool to trigger learning from experience. Disciplined reflection, challenging one’s assumptions and comfortable ways of thinking, leads to deeper learning. Unintentional learning can lead to intentional learning, only if it is identified by reflection. To make the informal and incidental learning more effective, managers can maintain learning logs, they can

keep journals, or they can review backward, which are some of the tools that can be used in the learning process. Such tools provide vital information in the process of reflection. In this regard, most importantly, managers may need organizational support and an appropriate environment in this process.

Informal development, alone, is insufficient; formal processes are needed, vis-à-vis.

Informal development, alone, is insufficient; formal processes are needed, vis-à-vis. When considered separately, both informal and formal MD processes have their own pros and cons. Evidence reveals that informal learning was often seen by managers themselves as actually preferable to various forms of planned MD (Mumford, 1997). Further, even if individuals work in organizations that have attempted various processes of formal MD, they nonetheless rated their informal experiences as much more significant. There can be several reasons as to why managers often find informal processes more effective than formal ones, such as, development programmes designed as off-the-job processes are experienced as unreal, irrelevant to the manager's priorities, or difficult to transfer the learning to manager's job; processes of learning attached to formal development programmes reflect interests of programme designers and do not take into account different individual learning preferences.

However, there are some deficiencies in the total reliance on a single process, formal or informal. Nicholson and West (1988, as in Mole, 2000, p. 78) conclude that organizations display an almost contemptuous neglect of the provision of formal aids to learning adjustment. It looks very much as if in most organizations, thinking about managerial development does not go beyond the "strategy" of throwing managers into the deep end to learn by themselves. This may produce adequate, and, on occasions, even excellent performance, but it leaves much to chance, is unlikely to establish a climate of attentiveness to career needs, and does nothing to establish either loyalty or controlled adjustment to performance requirements. Major deficiencies in total reliance on informal processes can be identified (Mumford, 1997). First, effective learning involves building successfully on properly understood past experience, not treating it as the only process of merit. Second, a carefully acquired experience of how to do a managerial job may well become out of date. Third, closest relationships with bosses and colleagues may be excellent providers of advice and good models of effective behaviour- or they may be neither. Fourth, though people develop skills from the "natural" processes of doing the job and finding out whether the way they do it works, the skill they have acquired may be inappropriate, and at worst, it may even be the wrong kind of skill. Finally, it is possible for a

manager's work experience to be extremely narrow in terms of jobs, functions, and kinds of organization and sizes of organization, but this does not mean that a manager should not learn about general aspects of management.

Therefore, on one hand, simple reliance on opportunities to learn from experience was not claimed to be the best answer to MD. Managers recognise gaps in their experience, and they could visualise the extent to which the opportunities could have been better recognised or the processes could have been better managed by their bosses. In this context, McGregor (1960) wrote, managers are grown- they are neither born nor made. The role of the company is to provide conditions favourable to faster growth. Hence, a distinguished feature of formal MD processes is that their effectiveness depends to a very large degree on the organization's climate and the active promotion and support of the top management.

Overall, a balanced view of MD should include the total process, which embraces the informal as well as formal processes. In this context, formal MD processes are important, but by definition, in the managerial world, insufficient. They are often inefficiently provided. Informal processes are both insufficient and inefficient, because managers often lack the skills to make the most of them as learning experiences. Therefore, it is not the view that formal MD is necessarily better than processes of learning on-the-job. Nor is it the view that simply because learning on-the-job is, in a sense, both natural and inevitable, that it should be relied on to the exclusion of formal processes. Therefore, the separation of formal MD from informal processes literally takes MD away from the reality of managerial work. Thus, the integrated approach to MD should make judicious use of both processes and should be integrated in terms of time, mental application, and even physical circumstances with managers' normal activities.

Formal MD processes

These are institutionally sponsored, planned, and deliberate processes, which are often monitored and controlled by people and forces other than the individual manager involved (Akuratiyagamage, 2004; Marsick and Watkins, 1997; Mumford, 1997). Several researchers support the claim that there is little awareness of the full range of formal processes that could be used (Woodall, 2000). All most all researchers have identified similar processes, such as, coaching, mentoring, action learning groups, project assignments, job rotation, self-development, as constituents of formal processes of MD that attempt at improving managerial

effectiveness through “planned and deliberate learning processes” (Armstrong, 1999; Storey, 1994; Peel, 1984; Mole, 2000; Woodall, 2000; Mumford et al., 1987; Mumford, 1997).

However, when comparing and contrasting one process with other processes of formal development, several problems arise. For example, rather general and loose distinctions are used between “formal development” and “self-development” and between “off-the-job” and “on-the-job” and “work-based and work-related” MD processes. Another example is how “on-the-job development” differs from “doing the job” (Thomson et al., 1997) or from “special projects” or “coaching”? In what way does a “special project” (Institute of Management, 1994) differ from an “in-company job rotation” (Thomson et al., 1997) or “special job placement” (Storey et al, 1997)? When different studies define different things, which sometimes overlap, ambiguities create several potential problems by making evaluation and comparison difficult (Woodall, 2000).

Another problem relating to formal MD processes is that when it comes to classifying formal MD processes into several categories, researchers come up with various categories (Armstrong 1999; Lawler et al., 1995; Mumford et al., 1987; Storey, 1994). For example, Armstrong (1999, 545) categorised formal MD processes into four categories, namely:

- development on the job through coaching, counselling, monitoring, and feedback by managers on a continuous basis, associated with the use of performance appraisal to identify and satisfy development needs
- development through work experience, which includes job rotation, job enlargement, taking part in project teams or task groups, action learning, and secondment outside the organization
- formal development by means of internal or external courses, and
- structured self-development by following self-managed learning programmes agreed as a personal development plan or learning contract, which may include guidance, reading, or the deliberate extension of knowledge or acquisition of new skills on the job, with a superior or an MD adviser

Storey (1994, p. 368) categorised formal processes into three groups, namely:

- structured development processes that are administered by some central agency and through which all must pass to achieve accreditation.

- self-development, following informal, unstructured ways of learning. Popular within this classification is the assumption that the individual “owns” the problem of his/her development, which is perhaps facilitated by means of the construction of either individual learning contracts or individual learning plans, and
- some intermediary process, whereby self-development is supported by organizationally provided mechanisms, which include systems of action learning, coaching, mentoring, and networking.

Lawler et al. (1995) categorised formal MD processes into four groups, namely:

- on-the-job programmes
- internal development programmes conducted by the firm’s own staff
- internal development programmes conducted by outside consultants, and
- external development programmes

Mumford et al. (1987, p. 16) categorised formal processes into four groups, namely:

- changes in jobs and job content (job redesign processes)- such as learning from job moves including job rotation, secondment, and promotion to a new job; allocating additional responsibilities or tasks; projects, committees, working parties, and task forces; assignments
- development processes within the job (on-the-job processes)- such as coaching, mentoring, counselling, monitoring, and providing feedback by the boss, and action learning
- activities external to the job (off-the-job processes), such as in-house off-the-job development courses, external off-the-job development courses, distance learning, interactive video, and group discussions that are organised by the company, and
- development activities planned by the individual rather than by the organization, such as modelling on the boss, modelling on colleagues or outsiders, and reading

By considering all the above categorisations of MD processes available, the writer finds that Mumford et al.’s (1987) categorisation provides relatively definite categories. Based on this categorisation, the concept and practice of formal MD processes can be briefly described as follows:

Formal MD does job redesign by identifying particular kinds of work that are available within and around the existing job. The formal development is effective when the job is actually fertilised, rather than treated as naturally fertile ground from which useful things grow. The fertilisation involves the construction of effective learning and development processes around the opportunities provided. Research evidence reveals that job redesign processes of MD are practised within organizations. Job rotation, as a means of job redesign, is prescribed as more suitable for only a small number of people as a means of deliberate preparation for general management rather than as a scheme to give general experience for a large number of people (Mumford 1997; Huczynski 1983). However, the evidence shows that Japanese MD provides good examples in the use of job rotation as a means of inducting managers to the organization, just after recruitment, from which both the individual and the organization can gain benefits (Storey et al., 1997). Learning from job moves in the form of secondment and promotion into a new organization is valued for the experience that can be gained by a manager. However, it is doubtful to what extent these processes can be used by organizations that do not have such facilities to move managers into jobs outside their employing organization. However, Japanese companies have used job moves to provide wide experience by not only moving managers to other companies in the group but also moving them to overseas job postings (Storey et al., 1997). Allocating additional responsibilities, projects, committees, working parties, and task forces as means of job redesign provides major potential development benefits (Mumford, 1997; Huczynski, 1983). However, simply providing these processes is not effective unless the available development opportunities are analysed, discussed, and the actual processes of learning are understood and employed by the manager involved. Unless the manager undergoing the development process is aware of the developmental objectives, he/she might be unable to get the full use of them. Thus, benefits to the individual as well as to the organization may be decreased as unintentional learning always has unintended learning consequences. However, assignments of short duration, as a means of job redesign, often fail to provide the intended learning, and also managers may receive incorrect feedback about the accuracy of their performance (Mumford, 1997). In consequence, the organization may also make a wrong judgment about the effectiveness of the manager involved.

Formal development processes within the job are concerned with the ways in which learning could be assisted, as distinct from job redesign, which reviews opportunities. These development processes represent an increasing trend towards helping the individual to take charge of his/her own learning. Therefore, the primary driver of the acquisition of knowledge

and skills becomes the manager, but the facilitator should be available to give guidance, insight, and encouragement in the learning process. Hence, it is important that individual managers are fully aware of the personnel gains from these, and both parties should have a clear understanding of their roles. While formal development processes are effective techniques of improving job performance in the short-term, they are more effective if they also take into account some of the long-term development needs of the individual. Hence, these processes could become most effective if they are part of a structured approach fully integrated into the organization's process of developing people. However, though organizations recognise the advantages these processes bring, the resource constraints could limit the time superiors can invest in their subordinates. However, in organizations where "fast track" promotion systems do not exist and where it is seen as part of the superiors' role to teach and develop subordinates, development processes within the job could have a record of success (Handy, 1987). Further, these processes could be developed as an integral part of the daily organizational life and could be used extensively at all levels of management.

As managers cannot learn within the job anything that is not available within or around it, they cannot develop skills that are not actually employed in the work environment. Therefore, development processes off-the-job have to be considered as complementary to other development processes. Off-the-job development processes are highly valued in instances where managers are required to achieve new skills that are not currently available within the organization or where there is no one available within the organization to demonstrate, coach, mentor, or facilitate development. As a means of MD, off-the-job processes have their own strengths and weaknesses. Therefore, it is beneficial to use a mix of in-company and external off-the-job development processes. In most instances, Asian countries prefer to use development processes off-the-job rather than on-the-job (Grzeda and Assogbavi, 1999). It is felt that the colonial and post-colonial structure of the general education of Asian countries, which is, in most cases, instructor-oriented and less learner-oriented, could have a considerable influence on the processes used for HRD, in particular, MD. However, in Japan, formal off-the-job development activities have typically not been seen as the main route to develop Japanese managers (Storey et al., 1997).

Development activities planned by the individual mainly include modelling on the boss, modelling on colleagues or outsiders, and reading. Though individuals have to take the main responsibility for his/her learning, this does not remove the responsibility of the organization

in providing a proper climate. Reading and modelling of the boss, colleagues, or outsiders as means of development processes planned by the individual will only become effective if they are integrated into a planned development scheme. It is said that in Japan, subordinates grow into managers by “watching their superiors’ backs” (Storey et al., 1997). The open-plan office arrangement, where managers are exposed to their subordinates, allows plenty of scope for this sort of learning. Reading as a part of a development programme may be a valuable way of gaining knowledge as long as the material is seen as relevant, and there is follow-up to ensure that learning has taken place. In encouraging learning by observing others, formal MD ought to include help on how to observe others at work and how to build review processes after the observation.

When considering criteria for selecting formal development processes, though there are varieties of formal MD processes available that can be used, none of the processes are superior to others (Mamoria 1998; Wills 1998). At the same time, there are numerous criteria that can be used in order to choose between different formal development processes. However, it is argued that there is no single, simple criterion that can be used to select a process. In this context, Huczynski (1983) states three bases that can be used in choosing formal development processes. Those are the objectives of the learning, the size of the group, and the level of student autonomy. Binsted, Stuart, and Long (1980) also presented some criteria for assessing and selecting development processes by their ability to deal with problems of transfer of learning into the learner’s work environment. The application of such criteria helps to narrow down the choice to manageable proportions. However, there are no main or only criteria that could be used in selecting the appropriate development process. Development contexts differ, and it may be that an entirely different set is appropriate elsewhere (Huczynski 1983). In this regard, the choice of the development process depends on several factors such as organizational culture and values, development purpose and content, the profile of learners and instructors, financial and technological resource availability, time, location, adaptability to learner differences, etc. But it is nevertheless important to use different processes rather than be wedded to a single one.

Trends in organizational approach to MD and challenges

An organization’s approach to MD has changed over the years, either from a wholly informal and unstructured to a formal system, or in terms of changes within an existing formal structure. Where organizations had moved from wholly informal and unplanned processes to more structured processes, the main cause for that was the belief or recognition that without

improving MD processes, the organization would not meet its objectives either now or in the future. Therefore, the major causes of changes in MD processes have been derived from changes in the business itself (Mumford et al., 1987). In Japan, their preference for MD processes has changed over time due to dramatic shifts experienced by the Japanese business sector, in 1995, when it shifted from a lifetime employment system to employability (Okazaki-Ward and Amaya 1996). The evolving new model of employment system has prompted the government to provide vocational skills and MD and managers to consider more on self-development activities, while companies are also conducting in-company MD programmes.

On the other hand, the preference attached to each formal development process can be changed over time. For example, attendance on courses in the 1980s to on-the-job development in the 1990s. However, such changes within an existing formal structure request better performance planning process and place increased responsibility on line managers and MD professionals. Thus, these trends could equally be interpreted as a sign of more focused management learning or of more fragmented management development (Barham et al., 1988), depending on the organizational support provided.

In this context, organizations can make considerable effort to upgrade the quality of the workforce continuously through the use of a mix of development processes instead of using a single one. Japanese MD is a mix of planned on-the-job development, self-development, and off-the-job development (Handy, 1987; Storey et al., 1997). Further, in the case of Vietnam, too, though their MD has primarily been based on formal lecture methods, with exposure to other approaches, formal MD programs in Vietnam have begun to incorporate a mix of development processes (McDaniel and Schermerhorn, 1999). However, in a similar vein, Lawler et al. (1995) reported that in Thailand the use of on-the-job development programmes was seen as a part of a sophisticated, broader strategy that emphasises multiple development processes. Yet firms in Thailand did not seem to be utilising a variety of formal development processes to a greater extent; they rely mostly on development programmes provided by outside vendors, which presumably do more by way of developing general skills than on-the-job development programmes. In the case of white-collar workers, firms in Thailand were less apt to use on-the-job programmes and more apt to use external programmes. Therefore, though such studies provide an idea about the nature of MD focus, it is also possible to find different MD processes in practice in different parts of the world. Further, it can also be observed that even within a particular country context, an enormous diversity of MD arrangements could be

identified (Smith and Hayton 1999). Enterprises in the same industry and serving similar markets would often be quite different in their approach to MD.

However, MD arrangements have important implications for human resource professionals. First, they need to be made more aware of the full range of MD processes, including developmental challenges, and how these relate to informal learning. Second, to achieve an effective system of formal MD, organizations have to take the responsibility of providing proper facilities for MD, as well as increase the manager's capacity and willingness to take control over and be responsible for him/herself and his/her own learning. Though planning, both formal and informal learning, enables individuals to nurture learning strategically and to take advantage of a wider range of learning strategies that might otherwise be overlooked, it should not be forgotten that there might be a range of factors that create problems. First, the process requires motivation, attitude, flexibility, and propensity to learn from the individual manager. Learners have to remain open to alternative frames of a problem, seek competing explanations, adopt an attitude of experimentation, and try on new behaviours for their own development. Second, the nature of the managers' jobs should offer opportunities to actually use the skills and competencies the manager has obtained. Therefore, the addition of new responsibilities and chances to experience jobs in other sections through planned job rotational schemes are all relevant to provide jobs that challenge the manager and offer new and interesting work experience. Third, organizations have to provide an environment that is conducive to learning. Organizations have to encourage, nurture, and support the development process, and have to promote the retention of new behaviours to make learning so much more effective and valuable. Organizations have to budget resources, especially time for MD. Only through organizational support systems, what individuals learn from the development processes will flow freely within the organizations to be captured and used by other organizational members.

Conclusion

In developing managers, the separation of formal MD from informal processes literally takes MD away from the reality of managerial work. Hence, in MD, both informal and formal processes have to be utilised. When considered separately, both informal and formal MD processes have their own pros and cons. Hence, there are some deficiencies in the total reliance on a single process, formal or informal. Therefore, the balanced view of MD should include the total process, which embraces informal as well as formal processes. However, to be

effective, both formal and informal learning have to be deliberately encouraged by an organization.

However, the most significant feature of informal processes is that, though these almost always take place naturally, managers are not always conscious that they are in developmental experiences at all. Therefore, though informal experiences are widely present and often provide the deepest and richest learning, they are often poorly identified and, as a consequence, insufficiently used. Therefore, informal learning has to be deliberately encouraged by an organization. Organizations can provide kinds of challenges that will provide opportunities to develop new skills/abilities. In the learning process, facilitators, peers, other colleagues, and managers from other organizations can be great sources of knowledge. On the other hand, managers have to integrate development into their lives on a continuous basis. Organizations have to provide an environment that is conducive to learning, where learning is encouraged, nurtured, and supported. Therefore, whatever development process is used, all processes have important implications for human resource professionals.

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